

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SUNDAY****FIRST NAME: RICHARD ALE****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing a good academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-10)
2. Some rules of thumb in writing a paper (EUCLID 2021, 12-14)
3. Using punctuation marks (EUCLID 2021, 17)
4. Variations in using American and British English (EUCLID 2021, 16-23)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have completed a review of the ACA-401D and the reading list. My review of the ACA-401D course pack is one of the best English writing preparatory materials I have ever read. The course provides a detailed foundation to communicate effectively in the English language. It is an essential preparatory course for students to embark on the PhD journey. I believe that by making International Academic Writing the first module, EUCLID made the best decision.

In my 17 years of experience in development work, I have written numerous reports and project proposals. However, the course materials have revealed to me that much of my writing was erroneous, especially in punctuation, mixing American and British English, and wrongly referencing other writers' material in text and reference lists. Therefore, the ACA-401D course has already proved its relevance and usefulness.

According to the ACA-401D course content, it is important to decide whether to use British or American English before starting to write an academic essay. In this response paper, I shall use British English because I am used to it and, therefore, more comfortable with it.

In this response paper, I will discuss five major concepts that I have learned from the ACA-401D course pack (period one): writing a good academic essay, some rules of thumb in writing a paper, using punctuation marks, variations in using American and British English, and plagiarism, and then conclude.

2) WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

Chapter One of the ACA-401D course pack guides students on how to write an essay. According to this chapter, while essay writing is not a strictly straightforward process, there are some basic steps in writing a good essay, and the course pack emphasizes the significance of starting early when writing an essay. There are times when I have started writing documents, such as progress reports, at the last minute, and they have almost invariably been returned with numerous queries due to the mistakes in them. Late starts in writing result in poorly structured documents, with grammatical errors, shoddy analysis, and mediocre answers. Therefore, the principle of starting the writing process early is important.

In the ACA-401D course pack, I have learned that when writing an academic essay, each paragraph in the body should deal with one issue. This has led me to realize that, in my previous academic writing, I sometimes dealt with multiple issues in a paragraph and that where I dealt with one issue in a paragraph, I did so unconsciously.

I have also learned that it is good practice to write an essay and keep it aside for a few days before editing it (EUCLID 2021, 11) because this can improve the quality of an essay significantly. This is particularly true and relevant in my field of work, which involves writing program and evaluation reports. Looking over my previous reports, I have realized that those that I wrote at the last minute were substandard and inadequately communicative. When I read my draft after a week, I could not believe the number of mistakes and incoherent sentences I found. The time allowance for editing has enabled me to rectify at least some errors in the draft. I, therefore, agree that this is a best practice in both academic and non-academic professional writing.

During my reading of Chapter One of the ACA-401D course pack, I realized the significance of an introduction and a conclusion in an essay. I have learned that while an essay introduction moves from the general to the specific, a conclusion moves from the specific to the general (EUCLID 2021, 10). An introduction should include a brief sentence or two introducing the topic, and it should state the key points to be discussed, but without the details. In conclusion, the writer should restate the answer to the question at hand, summarize key issues, and include a final broad statement for future directions or action to qualify the conclusion. I must admit that, in my earlier writing, while I always attempted to write clear introductions and conclusions, I had no such guidelines in mind. When I looked through my previous academic essays and professional reports, I realized that while the introductions somewhat met the above standards, the conclusions did not. To ensure that I follow these newly discovered guidelines, I have developed a checklist, which I now use to review my documents and those submitted to me for review.

3) SOME RULES OF THUMB IN WRITING A PAPER

I was engrossed in the ACA-401D course pack, especially the section on the rules of thumb in writing a paper, because it addresses many of the challenges I have grappled with in writing documents, including emails. The section emphasizes the importance of avoiding multiple sentences that begin with “It is...” or “There is...” In my writings, I normally have sentences that start similarly.

I have also discovered the reason why I use an excessive number of words in my sentences. As noted earlier, I have developed a checklist of all these writing errors to help me check and improve my academic and professional documents. With this checklist, I hope to transform my writing to an acceptable, international academic writing standard.

Verbosity has been my challenge, and while I have attempted to use computer applications to achieve brevity, I have always felt a need to develop this skill for fluency. That is why the module on international academic writing is particularly relevant to me, for it will help me to improve my academic and professional writing skills.

4) USING PUNCTUATION MARKS

One of the main reasons for my enrolling in this Ph.D. program was to be able to access this study module. As a monitoring, evaluation, and learning specialist, most of my work involves writing reports and other documents, and as a part-time consultant, I frequently write project feasibility, baseline surveys, and evaluation reports. Chapter Two of the ACA-401D course pack has revealed to me that I have been misusing punctuation marks. While reading this chapter, I looked back at my writings and found that I wrongly used a pair of commas to surround defining clauses. For example, “Young people, that were not trained in life skills, could not negotiate for safer sex.” As highlighted in the study materials, if I removed the defining clause in the above quotation, part of the meaning would be lost.

I also did not know how to use square brackets, and I used square brackets in place of round brackets, which is wrong according to Chapter Three of the study materials. While reading about the use of square brackets, I checked one of my past reports and found that, instead of using square brackets to add comments, corrections, or translations as highlighted in the study materials, I always used them to add extra information for non-defining clauses.

I have also learned that a semicolon is used to introduce a sub-clause that follows logically from the text before it (study materials ACA-401D), and this depends logically on the preceding main clause. A semicolon is also used to link two related parts of a sentence. While I used the same colon correctly, I did so without this guideline in mind. I only learned to use this by reading through the work of other people or writers, and therefore, I would not explain the principle behind this.

Yet another lesson I have learned is that double quotes can be substituted for single quotes, and vice versa, to merge the quote with the rest of the text (EUCLID 2021, 49). I have always used double quotes, wrongly thinking that single quotes are used differently. While reviewing Chapter Two on punctuations, I quickly opened three (3) emails to check how I had used exclamation marks, and I found out that I had always put a period after an exclamation mark, which is incorrect.

5) VARIATIONS IN USING AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

Uganda, my country of birth, was a British colony and still uses British English as the official language. While I am aware of the differences between British and American English, I have always mixed the two versions of English in my writing. While using Microsoft Word to author documents, words that are written differently in American and British English, like misspellings, are underlined in red if written in British English. During proofreading, I have always corrected this by selecting a spelling option which is normally in American English. As a result, my documents have always been written in both versions of English, which I now know to be wrong, thanks to the “International Academic Writing” course (EUCLID 2021, 27).

I am now very careful to use only one English version in every document I author, British English. To ensure that all my writings are in one English version, I have developed a tabulated checklist containing English words written differently in British and American English. This checklist, in this short period, has ensured that my documents use one English version to clearly communicate to my target audience.

6) PLAGIARISM

According to EUCLID (2021, 34), plagiarism is the use of a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. Examples of plagiarism include using someone else's ideas or words, which can be quotes or paraphrases, or copying and pasting information from the Internet without acknowledging the authors of such information. Not referencing information sources is, therefore, wrong and unethical, and as an academic offense, it can lead to grave penalties, for instance, a lower mark or failure. While I am now aware of the gravity of plagiarism in academic writing, I was previously unaware that acknowledging information sources when writing professional documents, like project proposals, was particularly important. For example, in 2008, I authored a proposal proposing to improve the quality of drinking water in schools by using sand to filter water. I used information from a blog written by an American master's degree student who had offered to help us look for funding if we wrote a good proposal about using sand to filter water. Still, I did not acknowledge indebtedness to the blog. As a result, we lost potential funding of over US\$ 10,000. Since then, I have taken plagiarism seriously when writing academic and professional documents.

According to EUCLID (2021, 35), when using a quotation, a writer must use quotation marks to indicate what the author said, and he or she must include the author's name and the number of the page from which the quotation is drawn. However, quotations that take longer than four lines have no quotation marks. According to EUCLID, long quotations should be indented to look like separate paragraphs. When I checked my earlier evaluation and research reports, I found quotation marks used on quotations that are longer than four lines. I have always used quotation marks on quotations as long as eight lines. While I now feel ashamed of these mistakes, I am pleased that I now know better, and I am confident that my future writing will be much more conventional and professional.

According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2021), it is important to limit the number of quotations in a research paper. When an excessive number of quotations are used in a professional paper, it does not look like the writer's own work. According to Cleenewerck and & Gulma, quotations are used when there is strong language in the quotation that emphasizes. During my reading of the chapter on plagiarism, I sampled some key evaluation and research reports that I had authored and found that, in those reports, I had used quotations even when there was no strong language. In my view, this module is the best foundation for both international academic writing and professional writing. I am certain that my future academic and development work will be written professionally.

7) CONCLUSION

Chapter Two (punctuation) of the study materials has been the most fascinating for me. It has revealed my previous misuse of punctuation marks and convinced me that my decision to undertake a Ph.D. program under EUCLID was judicious and timely. I have no doubt that I will sharpen my English- writing and communication skills and realize my career goals.

To ensure that I apply my newly acquired punctuation knowledge, I have developed a checklist that I am now using while reviewing my work and the works of my colleagues. When I crosschecked my work, I discovered that while I had stated that I had learned the correct usage of certain punctuation marks, I had still failed to use those marks correctly, and I corrected my mistakes.

While reading this inaugural course pack, I constantly referred to my previous writings, such as evaluation and research reports, and found that most of them were substandard. Therefore, I am already reaping the fruits of my Ph.D. program, and I am very excited about it.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent, Director. 2021. *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial*. Vimeo video.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed.* Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.